

Preparation of *p*-Diethylaminobenzaldehyde.

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An attempt has been made to prepare *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde in quantity. The patent of Böhringer (D. R. P. 108026) as recorded in Winther's Patente der Organischen Chemie was followed with modifications. In spite of many variations with regard to relative proportion of reactants and other details, nothing crystalline could be isolated. Methods for the preparation of alloxantin and alloxan from uric acid (*cf.* Biltz and Max, *Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 2451) and diethylanil-alloxan (*cf.* Pettizari, *Gazzetta*, 1887, **17**, 412) are recorded in the experimental sequel.

Ullmann and Frey (*Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 860; *cf. ibid.*, 1905, **38**, 524) obtained *p*-diethylaminobenzylidene-*p*-aminodimethylaniline (I, R = Me) by the interaction of diethylaniline, formaldehyde and nitroso-diethylaniline. We made an extensive study of this reaction

but could not isolate the aldehyde after the hydrolysis of (I, R = Me).

The substance (I, R = Et) was also prepared but it also did not give the aldehyde on hydrolysis. Further work is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the crystallisation of all the compounds described below, a little animal charcoal was used together with the solvent.

Uric acid (20 g.) and dilute hydrochloric acid (78 c. c.) were heated on a water-bath at 35-37°, and finely powdered potassium chlorate slowly sprayed into the mechanically stirred mixture until a clear solution was obtained. The cold solution was diluted with water (152 c. c.), allowed to stand (50 minutes) and then filtered. Through the filtrate a brisk current of sulphuretted hydrogen was passed for about 20 minutes, the solution left aside (22 hours), cooled in a frigidaire (2 hours) and filtered. The solid was washed with cold water, dissolved in hot water and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness (yellowish crystals, 15 g.). After two recrystallisations from hot water, colourless rhombic prisms were obtained, m. p. 201-202* (decomp.). (Found: C, 30.1; H, 3.0; N, 17.2. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_4$ requires C, 29.8; H, 3.1; N, 17.4 per cent).

* The melting points recorded were all determined in sealed tubes.

Alloxan.—Alloxantin (9 g.) was treated with a mixture of concentrated (12 g.) and fuming (18.5 g.) nitric acids and the mixture left in a fume cupboard for 5 days. The solid obtained was dried, yield 8.2 g. It was obtained as colourless crystals from hot water, m. p. 185-86° (decomp.). (Found : C, 22.6 ; H, 4.6 ; N, 13.2. $C_4H_{10}O_8N_2$ requires C, 22.4 ; H, 4.7 ; N, 13.1 per cent).

Diethylanil-alloxan.—To diethylaniline (16.4 g.) heated on a steam-bath and mechanically stirred, a strong hot aqueous solution of alloxan (16 g.) was added dropwise, when the mixture assumed a pink colouration and crystals gradually began to separate. After standing for 48 hours, the mixture was filtered, the solid washed with water and alcohol and dried, yield 22.3 g. It is insoluble in water but soluble in hot alcohol, from which it crystallises as colourless crystals, m. p. 194-95° (decomp.). (Found : C, 57.9 ; H, 5.7 ; N, 14.3. $C_{14}H_{17}O_4N_3$ requires C, 57.7 ; H, 5.8 ; N, 14.4 per cent).

p-Diethylaminobenzylidene-*p*-aminodimethylaniline. — Diethylaniline (5 g.), dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (32%, 10 c. c.) was added to a cold solution of formaldehyde (40%) and the mixture heated on a boiling water-bath for 15 minutes. Powdered *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline hydrochloride (5 g.) was then added. After a vigorous reaction the red solution was diluted with water (60 c. c.) and made alkaline with cold sodium carbonate solution (10%, 65 c. c.). After allowing to stand for 36 hours, the dark brown precipitate was filtered, washed with a mixture of alcohol and ether (1 : 1) and dried, yield 6.9 g. For further purification the compound was dissolved in alcohol and reprecipitated with water. It was obtained as greenish yellow crystals, m. p. 144-45°. (Found : C, 77.1 ; H, 8.5 ; N, 14.1. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{23}N_3$: C, 77.2 ; H, 8.4 ; N, 14.2 per cent).

p-Diethylaminobenzylidene-*p*-aminodiethylaniline. — A mixture of diethylaniline (15 g.), formaldehyde solution (40%, 9 c. c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c. c.) was heated on a steam-bath for 20 minutes. To the hot mixture freshly prepared *p*-nitrosodiethylaniline (6 g.) was added all at once. After the initial reaction had subsided, the solution was diluted with water to 200 c. c. and 15% caustic soda solution added until the red colour disappeared. The precipitated benzylidene compound was filtered, washed with dilute alcohol, crystallised from methyl alcohol, m. p. 147-49°. (Found : C, 78.4 ; H, 9.1 ; N, 12.8. $C_{21}H_{29}N_3$ requires C, 78.0 ; H, 8.9 ; N, 13.0 per cent).